

**The Use of Secondary Data in the Reconstruction of
Nigeria's Political History by Scholars and Researchers: A
Critical Appraisal of Some Literature**

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Abstract

The study examined the use of some secondary data in the reconstruction of Nigeria's historical past by scholars and researchers. It focused on some political issues and not a holistic analysis of Nigeria's political history. The aim of the study was to identify the misconceptions and misinterpretations that have been associated with secondary sources used in the interpretation of some of the political developments in the Nigeria state as far as their historicisation is concerned. It also discussed the need to curtail such erroneous views. The study posits that of all the sources available to scholars and researchers, secondary data appear to be the commonest and easily accessed. Used alongside other sources which is inimitable, caution and authentication of certain claims ought to be done by history scholars and researchers. The study adopted the narrative, descriptive and analytical approaches to the categories of historical works it examined and concludes that secondary data as valuable instruments of historicizing the past must be saved from extinction by preserving them and avoiding alteration in any form.

Keywords: Critical review, secondary data. Some literature, Nigeria and Political history.

Introduction

In the exercise of recording and interpreting past human action, various sources, otherwise called evidences are used. At the very beginning of the early historical researcher's inquiry different kinds of evidences or sources on which the researcher could base his assertions are used. Generally, the sources of historical evidence may be divided broadly into verbal and mute sources. Whereas verbal or speaking evidence is often, though not necessarily written, but exist as records. They could be written such as chronicles, annals, biographies, genealogies, memoirs, diaries and even inscriptions of certain kinds. They may also be oral such as ballads, anecdotes, tales, sagas, phonographs, and tape recordings. Portraits, historical paintings, scenic sculpture, coins, medals and certain kinds of films, kinescopes etc, also belong to verbal or speaking evidences used in historicisation works. Mute sources on the other hand, refers to objects such as buildings, drawings, tools, fragments of pottery and any physical object without words. A coin may belong to both kinds if it has an inscription on it. In spite of the ubiquity of these sources in the African continent, for a long time the continent's history hinged on eurocentricism.¹

The aforesaid sources are often described as being intentional transmitters of fact though it is recognised that all of them do not have direct historical intentions. The other groupings of sources of historical evidence are relics. These include: human remains, letters, literature, public documents, business records and types of inscriptions.² **Relics** provide “unconscious evidence” which make them invaluable part of historical narrative. On the whole however, historical source materials are classified into primary or secondary sources. As a basic rule, primary sources are all sources directly connected with the research area or topic, while secondary sources of data come from middlemen acting between the original witness and present consumers hence published books, newspapers, unpublished theses, monographs etc belong to this category. Secondary sources are used to bridge gaps between the various pieces of primary data. Thus, for secondary sources to produce desired results, their genuineness must be investigated by the researcher.

Interestingly Nigeria as a country has experiences a lot of events-from almagamation to independence and beyond. These developments covered all facts of the people’s past-political, economic, social and others. In all of these

developments, scholars from different disciplines have made efforts and thereby have enriched available literatures on issues. One area that have received commendable attention in the research efforts of scholars appears to be on political developments. Issues of political developments has attracted the research interests of historians and non-historians such that today, the quantity of works on Nigeria's political developments is astonishing. Yet, there seems to be some element of falsehood in some of the efforts so far made that depended on secondary data for their investigations.

For convinience, existing literature on political developments in Nigeria could be classified into: biographies and autobiographies of prominent Nigerians; those that concern political parties and elections in Nigeria; and those that concern democratic governance and its challenges in Nigeria. Of course, these works have made indellible contributions in understanding the historical past of the Nigeria state, yet extant evidences appear to contradict some of the views, submissions and conclusions of the available secondary sources on the political history of Nigeria. This study therefore, seeks to put in proper historical perspective, the conclusions of scholars and writers

who investigated issues of political development in the Nigeria State.

Biographies and Autobiographies:

Few topics have evoked as much controversy in the approach to the study of history as the subject of biography.³ The quality of the biographical studies produced on almost every person willing to sponsor them in Nigeria in the recent past⁴ speaks volume of the importance attached to biographical works. Ordinarily, biographies are accounts of peoples' life written by someone else.⁵ The increased importance attached to biographies was due to the fact that some persons believed that history is enshrined in the lives of great men.⁶ In fact, at a point it was said that "biography is the most universally pleasant, the most universally profitable, of all reading".⁷ R.W Emerson also added that "There is properly no history, only biography."⁸ Auto-biography writers have also argued vehemently that biography is constructed on principles that are not only non-historical but anti-historical thus leading to the claim that "at best, it is poetry, as its worst, an obstructive egotism, but history it can never be".⁹ These debate notwithstanding, a lot of biographical and autobiographical works have emerged in the Nigeria state. The list is voluminous. Examples include: *My Life: The*

*Autobiography of Sir Ahmadu Bello, Sardauna of Sokoto,*¹⁰ *Awo: The Autobiography of Chief Obafemi Awolowo,*¹¹ *My Odyssey: An Autobiography of Nnamdi Azikiwe,*¹² *A Right Honourable Gentleman: The Life and Times of Alhaji Sir Abubakar Tafawa Balewa,*¹³ *Dr. M.I. Okpara: A Biography,*¹⁴ *The Politics of Mallam Aminu Kano: Documents From the Independence Struggles, 1950-1960,*¹⁵ *The Life History of Herbert Macaulay (n.p.n.d)*¹⁶ *Ahmadu Bello, Sardauna of Sokoto: Values and Leadership in Nigeria.*¹⁷ and Olajide Aluko's *Ghana and Nigeria, 1957-1970, A Study in Inter-African Discord*¹⁸ A close look at some of the issues raised in these narratives would justify this study. In latter work mentioned above for instance, Olajide Aluko branded Sir Ahmadu Bello as an ethnic-conscious person who lived his life for the interest of Northern Nigeria. Even at his death in January 1966, Aluko claimed that Ahmadu Bello "refused to become a Nigerian"¹⁹ Basically, Olajide Aluko never gave grounds for his submission.²⁰

However, it appeared that throughout the political career of Ahmadu Bello, the interest of the Northern Region seemed superior to that of the Nigeria nation. Instances abound. For example, at the eve of Nigeria's independence, he was vehement that the consolidation of the North was what was uppermost in

his mind.²¹ To demonstrate this point, his autobiography that was written in 1961 and published the following year did not refer to national independence. The book ended thus: “I think it fitting to bring my narrative to an end with grant to us of our long-sought self government”. The ‘self government’ here, obviously was not the national one of October 1960, but the one granted to Northern Nigeria in 1959.²² Views have been expressed too, that Ahmadu Bello was not alone in this direction. Other leaders did it. In 1948, Tafawa Balewa had very early in the nationalist struggle expressed doubt about the possibility of a united country when he said:

“Many Nigerians speak of Unity. They are well too loose about it. Many of them deceive themselves by thinking that Nigeria is one. This is wrong, particularly, some of the press people with chance of writing in papers to tell the whole world that this is one country. When they give lectures, they shout it out that Nigerians are one people. This is wrong. When I look around in the council, I see Honourable members of all parts of Nigeria...sitting together and am bound to feel some presence of unity. But, I am sorry to

say that the presence of unity is artificial and it ends outside this chamber.²³

In fact by 1959, Tafawa Balewa had claimed that he was determined and prepared to die for the cause of Northern Nigeria.²⁴ Before then, ten years earlier, Nnamdi Azikiwe had declared that:

It would appear the God of Africa has created the ibo nation to lead the children of Africa from the bondage of ages...The martial powers of the ibo nation at all stages of human history has enabled them not only to conquer others but also to adapt themselves to the role of preserve.²⁴

As one would expect, Chief Obafemi Awolowo on his part, also went ahead to praise the Yorubas and even claimed that one must be a tribalist before becoming a nationalist. These points appeared not to have been considered by Olajide Aluko before labeling Ahmadu Bello the way he did. Ahmadu Bello had in a New Year Message, called on Nigerians to “think and act as Nigerians...the interest of the state should and indeed take

precedence over those of the tribe or those of political groupings”.²⁵

Political Parties and Elections in Nigeria:

As earlier stated in this study, the second category of works to be discussed are those that concern political parties and elections (a few of them though) in Nigeria. Of concern in this study is the work of Babatunde Sofela.²⁶ In this work, the author made an analysis of the effort made by the Action Group Party to form alliance with some smaller parties in Northern Nigeria. In the work, the author stated that Chief Obafemi Awolowo, the leader of the party, was not favourably disposed to the idea of alliances. In his words: “the formation of alliances ran against the grain of the AG leadership.”²⁷ This view obviously appear misleading. Rather, evidence available indicate that the Action Group Party had alliance, with northern minority parties such as the United Middle Belt Congress (UMBC) and the Borno Youth Movement (BYM). In fact, Obafemi Awolowo did his best to bring into fruition an NCNC-AG alliance in the central legislature after the federal elections of 1959. According to Awolowo, on December 21, 1959:

“I hereby declare to the general public of
Nigeria that i did everything that was

Humanly possible (including conceding the Prime Ministership to Dr. Azikiwe) and Compatible with honour to effect an Action Group-NCNC parliamentary coalition in the Federal Legislature”.²⁸

The claim of Awolowo as shown in the above statement was authenticated by Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe in a meeting he had with executives of his NCNC in Lagos, when he said: “the AG did everything that was humanly possible and compatible with honour to effect a coalition between the AG and the NCNC”²⁹ but the NCNC refused. In the circumstance therefore, Obafemi Awolowo could not have opted to be in opposition since he agreed that “...it is not a pleasant thing to be in opposition.”³⁰ Again, during the Second Republic, the Unity Party of Nigeria (which was a recrudescence of the Action Group Party) made attempts to form a Progressive Parties Alliance (PPA) for the 1979 and 1983 general elections.

Again, Sofela’s argument that the motion for independence by Anthony Enahoro on the floor of the Federal House of Representatives was done without Enahoro having knowledge of AG leadership, also seem misleading. Sofela had

claimed that “the motion was filed without the knowledge of the Leader or Deputy Leader and without prior submission to the AG’S Parliamentary Council for discussion.”³¹ Babatunde Sofela averred that the Parliamentary Council of the Action Group Party and its Executive Committee came to the conclusion that the technical branch of the party’s rule be jettisoned given the fact that the motion had an overriding policy decision of the Benin Conference. Second, was the fact that the withdrawal of the motion under discussion was moved in the Federal House on March 31, 1953 by Chief Anthony Enahoro in which he sought for the attainment of self-government by 1956.³² This line of reasoning no doubt, must have inspired Richard Sklar’s earlier submission that Anthony Enahoro’s motion “was filed without the knowledge of the Leader or Deputy Leader and without prior submission for the AG’s Parliamentary Council for discussion.”³³

The views expressed above seems misleading because according to Enahoro, “...although, the self-government motion was moved by me, it was actually a motion of the Action Group...the Action Group was a thorough and disciplined party. I could not have moved a motion of such magnitude without the consent and approval of my party”.³⁴ Existing evidence indicate

that Chief Obafemi Awolowo and Ahmadu Bello had discussed the motion as to whether to move it or not, on three distinct occasions before it was moved and opposed. As Ahmadu Bello put it:

“...on behalf of Northern members, I and another Minister approached the leader of the AG and Asked him to withdraw the motion before it was Debated as Northern members required time to Consult people of the North on this point as no Mandate had been given them by the people to discuss such a major question...After lengthy discussion, the leader of the Action Group replied that he could not ask the mover of the motion to withdraw, nor agree to any amendment.”³⁵

As pointed out by Oyeleye, the self government motion of 1953 had been adopted by the Action Group Party in their Annual Convention held in December 1952.³⁶ This fact was confirmed by Enahoro himself,³⁷ and re-affirmed by Ahmadu Bello.³⁸ Flowing from the aforesaid, the view that the self-government motion as espoused by Sofela, was filed without prior submission to the Action Group Party’s Parliamentary Council for discussion is misplaced and misleading.

Furthermore, the inability of Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe from becoming Leader of Government Business in the defunct Western Region also appears to have been attached to ethnic and partisan outlook by scholars. This also calls for re-examination. One could recall that the first general elections under the Macpherson constitution took place in the Western Region between August and September 1951. Ordinarily, the NCNC had anticipated to win 50 out of the 80 seats at stake in the election;³⁹ but the outcome elicited claims and counter-claims. Whereas the *Daily Service* (which was pro-AG) announced that the Action Group Party won 41 seats, NCNC 13, Independents 12, Ibadan People's Party 6, the *West African Pilot* (that was pro-NCNC) announced a different result. It announced that the NCNC won 32 seats, AG 27, Independents 8, while 5 results were being awaited.⁴⁰ The confusion that set in was clear: which party could be said to have won the highest number of seats in that election? This reasoning was at the centre stage until January 1952 when the constituted Western House of Assembly had its first sitting. The problem of how party members were to sit in the parliament also came. Before then, traditional ruler and followers of the *Egbe Omo Oduduwa* had worked on successful candidates but were not fully decided on the side of the House "to pitch their

tent”. It was even the case that Chief Obafemi Awolowo stood outside the Parliament building and insisted that he and his supporters (party members) would not enter the building except sitting arrangement in the parliament was done on party basis. This intrigue worked out and at the end Chief Awolowo emerged as the leader of Government Business in the Western Region.

It is important to quickly point out as it were, that given the fact that representation in the central legislature was based on electoral College system, political parties that were in power in each of the regions had to elect its representatives from its base. The implication of this was that only members of the majority party could be elected into the federal parliament. But as it turned out then, the federal capital (Lagos) had two seats in the federal parliament and the National Council of Nigeria and Camerouns party, which was the minority party in the Western House of Assembly, won all the five seats which implied that the Western House that was dominated by the Action Group Party had to send two NCNC members to represent Lagos in the central legislature. The two Lagos were scrambled for, by three NCNC candidates- Dr Nnamdi Azikiwe, Mr. Adeleke Adedoyin and Dr. Olorun-Nimbe. Matters got worsened because Olorun-Nimbe and Adedoyin flagrantly refused to step down for Dr

Nnamdi Azikiwe, the National President of the NCNC.⁴¹ Amidst this confusion; the NCNC had no option than to send the names of all the five Lagos NCNC members (who won the Lagos seats) to the Western House of Assembly in order to get two of them elected to the federal legislature. Expectedly, the votes showed that Dr, Olorun-Nimbe and Adeleke Adedoyin (who were both yoruba) were elected⁴²-a development that crushed the ambition of Azikiwe becoming the Leader of Government Business in the Western House of Assembly and being elected to the federal parliament.

The aforesaid incident has elicited different interpretations from scholars. Obaro Ikime claimed in his view that "...an igbo man (Zik) resident in Lgos contested elections there and swept the polls. Ethnic chauvinism prevented him being elected from the Western House of Assembly to the Federal House of Assembly to the Federal House of Representatives."⁴³ Professor Chinua Achebe has even accused Chief Awolowo of "stealing the government of western Nigeria from Dr. Azikiwe in 1951."⁴⁴ A careful consideration of the aforementioned episode would reveal something different entirely. The whole matter appeared to have been more of party indiscipline than ethnicity as suggested by the aforesaid erudite

scholars. Given the fact that the NCNC had won the five seats in Lagos, ordinarily there should not have been any problem getting two of its members into the central legislature. What could have happened was that the party should have met and decided which of its five elected members was to go to Lagos and thereby forward such names to the Western House of Assembly. This would have prevented the chances of the Action Group Party controlled House to choose by ballot. Consequently, the problem of indiscipline within the NCNC made it to play into the 'trap' of the Action Group Party. This point was even acknowledged by Dr Azikiwe during the party's convention in Kano in 1951 when he described the episode as tragedy for which the Action Group Party was not responsible.⁴⁵

It needs to be noted too that the 1951 election was not conducted on party basis. Rather, candidates contested and won on their individual strength,-a kind of 'zero-party' arrangement. It is a clear ignorance and spurious claim for writers or researchers to assert that candidates for the said election did so on political party basis. This aspect was put to rest when the then Public Relations Officer of the Nigerian Government, Harold Cooper, asked all the political parties contesting the elections to

submit the list of candidates who had what at best could be described as “working relationship with them.”⁴⁶

Representative Government in Nigeria:

All over the world today, democracy as a form of government has become popular essentially due to the fact that it guarantees political participation and protects the rights of citizens. Yet, some Nigerian writers have posited that representative government, especially adversarial democracy is strange to Africa. one of the adherents of this reasoning is the celebrated Professor of History, E. Adiele Afigbo. He claimed that the proximate cause of the travails of Nigerian democracy is the fact that it was imposed by Nigerians from outside and that it did not evolve on the basis of need. He stated further that western democracy in Nigeria is a plant of recent growth. According to him, democracy:

“has no ancestors or parents in indeigenous Nigerian political culture. Its sponsors were the western European bourgeoisie who introduced it in the first place and then retreated beyond the shores of Africa. The other sponsors are local intelligentsia, men and women alienated from their people and

society by their education; travels and tastes.”⁴⁷

The view of Professor Afigbo as expressed above may be accepted in part, but not as a whole. The age of democracy in Nigeria may be recent in terms of its growth, but to claim that democracy had no ancestors or parents in indigenous Nigerian political culture is spurious. Basically, village or traditional democracy was the ancestor of modern democracy, not only in Africa but in the entire world. The ancient Greek city-states illustrated this point.⁴⁸ Even in old Oyo empire, there existed a traditional democracy with well defined checks and balances. At the helms of affairs, was the Alafin, who though had powers, could be checked of his excesses and in fact, asked to commit suicide by pronouncement from the Bashorun. This was a counterweight against monarchical absolutism.

Conclusion:

This study has thrown up issues that need urgent attention. Put simply, six major points have been brought to the fore. These are essentially findings and misconceptions about the use of secondary sources in historicisation exercise among Nigerian Political historians and scholars. First, in the autobiographical work of Olajide Aluko, the picture painted

about Ahmadu Bello is that he was an ethnicist. This was not substantial because the same person so branded persistently emphasised that state interest as it were, should come before tribe or political affiliations. Second, on political parties and elections in Nigeria, Professor Babatunde Sofola had posited that Chief Anthony Enahoro did not have knowledge of Action Group Party's leadership before moving the motion for self-governance. This may have misled Richard Sklar who submitted that Chief Anthony Enahoro filed his motion for self-governance without knowledge of his leader and party members. Rather, as he, Enahoro, later affirmed, it was a motion of the Action Group Party.

Third, misconception also seemed to have trailed the inability of Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe becoming leader of Government Business in the former Western Region of Nigeria. This claim is also parochial and tainted with partisan outlook such that erudite scholars like Obaro Ikime could now believe ethnic chauvinism prevented Nnamdi Azikiwe from being elected from the western House of Assembly to the Federal House of Representatives. The episodes, as shown in this study were more of party indiscipline than ethnicity.

Fourth, it is also important to point out that the 1951 election to the Western House of Assembly was said to have been conducted on party basis. This was also misleading. Instead, candidates contested and won on their strength as was later explained by the then, Public Relations Officer of the country, Harold Cooper. Fifth, is the misleading information about democracy in Africa. Democracy is claimed to be strange to Africa by E. Adiele Afigbo. He even said it was imposed on the Nigerian peoples. This is not true because evidence exist in pre-colonial Nigeria, where for instance, in the old Oyo empire, checks and balances existed to curtail the excesses of rulers.

It needs to be quickly stated too that the political history of most ethnic groups in pre-colonial Nigeria have also made claims that are misleading. For example, early studies about the Ughievwen people of Western Delta, Nigeria written by Godini .G. Darah asserted that the people migrated in ‘one swoop’ from Ogobiri in Bayelsa state of Nigeria.⁴⁸ Yet, another researcher, M.Y. Nabofa, postulated that “Urhobo do not trace their origin to a common ancestor nor did any military force appear to wield them with force.”⁴⁹ Recent study by this author has thrown more light on these claims.⁵⁰ The study identified four influences and directions concerning the early history of the Ughievwen people-

the oriental tradition, (Middle East Claim), the Ogobiri strand, the movement from Benin Kingdom and the Niger-Benue Confluence Strand. The study claimed that in the absence of archaeological works not having been done in that of Nigeria, it suggested a settlement period of the people on their present abode to about the early decades of the 18th century and not in one ‘swoop’ relying on the king list of the royal family.

Flowing from the foregoing, it is obvious that the writing of history depends on sources but such must be properly scrutinized and even preserved to avoid misinterpretations and alterations. Secondary sources in History, as earlier stated especially with regards to Nigeria’s political history appear to be most common. They should be clearly stated and preserved.

Endnotes:

1. Okon .E. Uya; *African History, Some Problems in Methodology and Perspectives*, (Calabar: Cats Publishers, 1973), 4.
2. Other categories of relics are: language, customs, institutions, tools and other artifacts.
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4. R.T. Akinyele; “Biography as History”...26
5. *Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English*, (England: Longmans, 3rd edition, 1955), 116.
6. Thomas Carlyle, *History of the French Revolution III*, cited in E.H. Carr, *What is History*, (London: Penguin Books, 1979), 49.
7. J. Wood, (Rev.), *Dictionary of Quotations*, (London: Frederick Warne and Company Ltd, 1914), 30.
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9. R.G. Collingwood, *The Idea of History*, 5th Edition; (London: Longmans, 1962), 304.
10. Ahmadu Bello, *Sardauna of Sokoto*, (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1962).
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12. N. Azikiwe; *My Odyssey: An Autobiography of Nnamdi Azikiwe*, (Ibadan: Spectrum Books, 1970)
13. Trevor Clark; *A Right Honourable Gentleman; The Life and Times of Alhaji Sir Abubakar Tafawa Balewa*, (Zaria: Haudahuda Publishing Company, 1991).

14. Chris Offodile; *Dr M.I. Okpara: A Biography* (Enugu: Fourth Dimension Publishing Company, 1980)
15. Alkasum Abba; *The Politics of Mallam Aminu Kano: Documents From the Independence Struggles, 1950-1962*, (Zaria: Hudahuda Publishing Company, 1986).
16. Thomas Isaac, *The Life of Herbert Macaulay*, (n.p.n.d).
17. John Paden; *Ahmadu Bello, Sardauna of Sokoto: Value and Leadership in Nigeria*, (Zaria: Hudahuda Publishing Company, 1986).
18. Olajide Aluko; *Ghana and Nigeria, 1957-1970: A Study in Inter-Africa Discord*, (London: Rex Collins Ltd, 1976).
19. F.A.O Schwarz Jnr; *Nigeria: The Tribes, the Nation or the Race-The Politics of Independence*, (Cambridge: The M.I.T Press, 1965), 113.
20. Certain considerations may have influenced this. First, is the fact that Ahmadu Bello probably saw Lagos which was then the Federal Capital incompatible with his ideology; Second, his aristocratic background and personality could have rendered useless any attempt at pursuing compromise; and third was the fact that he may have looked forward to being the spiritual head of muslims in the country, a position he considered greater than that of the President or Prime Minister. See “Great Day for the North” and “Celebrations in the West”, *West African Review* January 1958, 227.

21. See Legislative Council Debates, March 4, 1948, 227.
22. *West African Pilot* January 10, 1959.
23. See the Presidential Address to the Ibo State Union; quoted in Remi Anifowose, *Violence and Politics in Nigeria; The Tiv and Yoruba Experience*, (New York and Enugu: NOK Publishers, 1982), 35.
24. Quoted by Emmanuel .O. Ojo, “Political Development in Nigeria: A Critique of Some of the Available Secondary Sources” *Jalingo Historical Review*, Vol. 1, No 2, 2011, 175.
25. As quoted by E.O. Ojo..., 175
26. Babatunde Sofela; “The Orign and Problems of a Nigerian National Party, 1951-1965”, *African Studies Review*, Vol. 6, June, 2007.
27. *The Daily Service*, December 22, 1959, and repeated in the edition of December 23, 1959.
28. *Nigerian Tribune*, February 15, 1959.
29. Emmanuel .O. Ojo, “The Nigerian Democratic Process: Ethnicity and Formation of Alliances”, Unpublished Ph.D Thesis, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, 2012, 231-244.

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31. Richard Sklar; *Nigerian Political Parties: Power in a Emergent African Nation*, (Enugu: NOK Publishers, 1983), 276.
32. Interview with Chief Anthony Enahoro, c.85, at No33 King George V Road, Onikan, Lgos, 22/8/2009 as quoted by Emmanuel .O. Ojo, “Political Development in Nigeria...”, 186.
33. Emmanuel .O. Ojo, “Political Development in Nigeria...”, 186
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35. Oyeleye Oyediran, *Nigerian Constitutional Development*, (Ibadan: Oyeniran Consults International, 2007), 24.
36. Ahmadu Bello; *My Life: The Autobiography of Sir Ahmadu Bello, Sardauna of Sokoto*, (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1962), 115.
37. Intervi with Chief Enahoro..., 22/8/2009
38. *West Africa*, January 6, 1951
39. *Daily Times*, January 5, 1952

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41. Quoted from K.O. Mbadiwe, “Vision of the Third Republic”, *Nigerian Guardian*, September 21, 1989.
42. Chinua Achebe, *The Trouble with Nigeria* (Enugu: Fourth Dimension Publishers, 1983), 58.
43. Obaro Ikime; Inaugural Address to the 30th Conference of the Historical Society of Nigeria (HSN) held at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka May 1, 1985, 23.
44. *Daily Times*, 21 September, 1951
45. Nnamdi Azikiwe, “The Price of Liberty”, *West African Pilot*, January 4, 1952.
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47. Quoted from J.E Casely-Hayford, *Gold Coast Institutions with Thoughts Upon a Healthy Imperial Policy for the Gold Coast and Ashanti*,(London: Frank Cass Co. Ltd, 1970), 33.
48. G.G. Darah, “Ughievwen” in O. Otite (ed.)*The Urhobo People* (Ibadan: Gold Press Ltd, 2011), 285.

49. M.Y. Nabofa, “Igbe Ubiesha: An Indigenous Charismatic Movement of the Urhobo People” in P.P. Ekeh (ed.) *Studies in Urhobo Culture* (New York, 2005), 370.

50. F.E. Oghi, “The Transformation of Ughievwen Clan in Urhobo Land, c.1800-1900”. An Unpublished Ph.D Thesis, Department of History and International Studies, University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria. November 2014, 59-63.